

X-Band Electron Paramagnetic Resonance Spectra of Amino Acid-Copper(II) and Amino Acid-Copper(II)-Imidazole Systems

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The binary complexes with amino acids and ternary complexes with amino acids and imidazole of Cu^{II} have been studied through epr spectral studies at different pH values. The complexes show superhyperfine lines on the g_{\perp} features in accordance to the number of nitrogens coordinated to copper.

In the present communication, we report X-band epr spectra of amino acid-copper(II) (1 : 1) and amino acid-copper-imidazole (1 : 1 : 1) for three amino acids (AA), viz. L-histidine (L-his), aspartic acid (aspA), glutamic acid (glutA) and three imidazoles, viz. imidazole (im), 2-methylimidazole (m-im) and 2-ethylimidazole (e-im).

Histidine is a biochemically important ligand having an ambidentate nature. L-Histidine binds to metal ions through the nitrogen at position-3, amino nitrogen and the carboxylic group. Aspartic acid and glutamic acid, both have three potential coordination sites, viz. the amino nitrogen and two carboxylate groups.

The potentiometric and spectrophotometric studies on ternary complexes of copper(II) with L-histidine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid as primary ligands and substituted imidazoles as secondary ligands have been reported by us earlier¹. The epr studies of ternary complexes of copper(II) with bovine serum albumin and amino acids² and also with glycylglycine and imidazoles have also been reported^{3,4}.

Results and Discussion

Binary system : The epr parameters obtained from the spectra of $\text{glutA-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{aspA-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ at different pH values are given in Table 1. For both the amino acids, the epr spectra show two epr features, one dominating at low pH values and the other at high pH values (Fig. 1(1)), which may be interpreted as follows. The formation of CuL_2 even for 1 : 1 Cu-ligand ratio was observed by Perrin and Sharma⁵ for copper histidine system. Two tridentate ligands form six-coordinated octahedral copper(II) complex. This finds further support from the fact that when the copper-amino acid ratio is raised to 1 : 2, the equilibrium shifts towards lower pH value (Fig. 1(2)). Copper(II)-glycylglycine complex³ show broadening of the epr lines at high pH values possibly due to formation of hydroxo-bridged species. The present systems, i.e. copper(II)-aspartic acid and copper(II)-glutamic acid, show sharp epr signals at high pH values (pH 10.5). This observation provides strong support for the formation of six-coordinate CuL_2 species at high pH. The octahedral species are much less susceptible to either hydrolysis or bridged species formation.

Ternary systems : The epr spectra of $\text{glutA-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ -imidazole (1 : 1 : 1) system with three imidazole at different pH values are shown in Fig 1(3). For aspartic acid and L-histidine the spectra show similar features. The epr parameters are given in Table 2. Drawing parallel with the work of Sato *et al.*⁶ on glygly-copper(II)-imidazole (1 : 1 : 1) several structures may be proposed for the ternary complexes under study. These are formed by the replacement of one water molecule from amino acid- $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}_2$ by imidazole.

At pH 5.50, the spectra of ternary systems $\text{AA-Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-m-im}$ or e-im (1 : 1 : 1) system exhibit g_{\parallel} lines in the same positions as in the spectra of binary system AA-Cu^{II} . It is, therefore, evident that with 2-methyl- and 2-ethylimidazole ternary complexes are not formed at this pH. With imidazole, however, at this pH there is no remainder of the g_{\parallel} signals of the binary system. Instead new g_{\parallel} signals appear

Fig. 1. Epr spectra of (1) $\text{GlutA-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ (1 : 1) system (ll region only), (2) $\text{GlutA-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ (2 : 1) system (ll region only) and (3) $\text{GlutA-Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-im}$ (1 : 1 : 1) system; each component 1×10^{-3} M.

Fig. 2. Epr spectra (\perp regions only, expanded scale) of (1) L-his-Cu^{II}-im (1 : 1 : 1) and (2) GlutA-Cu^{II}-im (1 : 1 : 1)

at higher magnetic field. These may be attributed to the ternary complex. Thus imidazole ternary complex formation takes place even at pH 5.5. At pH 7.15, all AA-Cu^{II}-im systems show signals corresponding to the ternary system only, i.e. ternary complex formation is complete by now. These observations suggest that the ternary complex formation with imidazole is complete at pH < 7, whereas with 2-methyl- and 2-ethylimidazole it is complete at pH > 7. These observation are in line with the relative pK values of three imidazoles³ : imidazole (pK = 7.1) < 2-methylimidazole (pK = 8.2) \approx 2-ethylimidazole (pK = 8.2).

TABLE 1—EPR PARAMETERS FOR AA-Cu^{II} (1 : 1 AND 2 : 1) SYSTEMS

System	pH	First type signal				Second type signal			
		g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel} (G)	A_{\parallel} (mk)	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel} (G)	A_{\parallel} (mk)
AspA-Cu ^{II} (1 : 1)	5.50	2.30	2.04	160	16.9	2.29	2.07	180	18.6
	7.15	2.28	2.02	160	16.9	2.23	2.07	175	18.2
	8.50					2.23	2.06	177	18.4
	10.50					2.23	2.06	176	18.4
(2 : 1)	5.50					2.22	2.02	168	17.4
	7.15					2.23	2.02	172	17.9
	10.50					2.22	2.01	175	18.1
GlutA-Cu ^{II} (1 : 1)	5.50	2.29	2.05	160	16.9	2.26	2.07	180	18.6
	7.15	2.27	2.02	160	16.9	1.23	2.07	175	18.2
	8.50					2.22	2.06	175	18.2
	10.50					2.22	2.06	175	18.1
(2 : 1)	5.50					2.22	2.06	175	18.1
	7.15					2.22	2.06	175	18.1
	8.50					2.22	2.06	175	18.1
	10.50					2.22	2.06	178	18.4

TABLE 2—EPR PARAMETERS FOR AA-Cu^{II}-IM (1 : 1 : 1) SYSTEMS

System	pH	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel} (G)	A_{\parallel} (mk)
L-his-Cu ^{II} -im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.23	2.07	170	17.5
	7.15	2.22	2.06	180	18.6
	8.50	2.22	2.06	180	18.6
L-his-Cu ^{II} -m-im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.25	2.08	160	16.8
	7.15	2.21	2.07	186	19.2
	8.50	2.21	2.06	184	19.0
L-his-Cu ^{II} -e-im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.26	2.09	165	17.4
	7.15	2.22	2.06	183	19.0
	8.50	2.22	2.07	182	18.7
AspA-Cu ^{II} -im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.23	2.06	170	17.7
	7.10	2.22	2.06	178	18.5
	10.50	2.23	2.06	175	18.2
AspA-Cu ^{II} -m-im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.23	2.06	160	17.0
	7.10	2.22	2.07	178	17.7
	10.50	2.23	2.06	177	18.2
AspA-Cu ^{II} -e-im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.27	2.06	166	18.0
	7.10	2.22	2.06	177	18.1
	10.50	2.21	2.06	178	18.1
GlutA-Cu ^{II} -im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.23	2.07	170	17.7
	7.10	2.22	2.07	175	18.1
	10.50	2.23	2.07	175	18.2
GlutA-Cu ^{II} -m-im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.26	2.08	155	16.3
	7.10	2.23	2.06	180	18.7
	10.50	2.22	2.06	184	19.1
GlutA-Cu ^{II} -e-im (1 : 1 : 1)	5.50	2.26	2.08	155	16.3
	7.10	2.22	2.06	175	18.1
	10.50	2.23	2.07	175	18.2

Superhyperfine lines : The g_{\perp} region of the spectra of ternary systems show well-defined superhyperfine lines with overshoot. Following the method of Bereman and Kosman⁷, the following values for various epr parameters (Table 3) have been obtained from the spectra for the g_{\perp} region with expanded magnetic field scale (not shown here).

TABLE 3

System	$A_{N_{\parallel}}$ (G)	$A_{N_{\perp}}$ (G)	A_{N_0} (G)
Galactose-Cu ^{II} -im ^a	12.1	15.7	13.4
L-his-Cu ^{II} -im	12.0	15.0	13.5
AspA-Cu ^{II} -im	12.2	15.7	13.1
GlutA-Cu ^{II} -im	12.1	15.0	13.5

^aRef. 7.

Seven g_{\perp} superhyperfine lines (Fig. 2) in the case of the histidine system and five g_{\perp} superhyperfine lines in the cases of aspartic acid and glutamic acid are in line with the proposed structure of the ternary systems :

Experimental

The stock solution of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving copper(II) perchlorate hexahydrate (Aldrich) in double-distilled water. The pH of sample solution was adjusted by adding small quantities of 1 M NaOH and 1 M HCl. After adjusting the pH to a desired value, the solution

was allowed to stand at room temperature at least 10 min before being frozen in liquid nitrogen. The pH values of all samples were routinely checked before and after the epr measurements. The frozen solutions were placed in a Varian liquid nitrogen insert Dewar flask for measurements at liquid nitrogen temperature.

The epr spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century Series spectrometer, equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band 100 kHz modulation. Solid diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was used as field marker. The g_{\parallel} and A_{\parallel} values were measured according to the standard procedure⁸.

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